

Neuroplasticity and cognitive development: Interdisciplinary perspectives on psychotherapeutic and educational approaches

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Dear Readers,

Undoubtedly, the primary interest of the "*Advances in Medicine, Psychology, and Public Health*" journal is to initiate a serious debate among various disciplines, notably psychology, medicine, and public health, without confining itself to a particular trend [1]. However, today's debate, which divides the scientific community and demands an empirical response, revolves around the foundations of psychotherapeutic and educational protocols. The question is as follows: Should we continue to believe that our mental functions are localized in specific brain areas and generate specific domains for information processing? And if so, where does this specificity come from? Is it genetically determined? Alternatively, with recent advancements in brain imaging and artificial intelligence, is it challenging to discuss specificity in cognitive domains and brain regions? Ultimately, what should be the focus of our discourse?

We are thus faced with two hypotheses. The first is called the neurosurgical hypothesis, and the second is termed the neuroconstructivist hypothesis. According to the neurosurgical hypothesis, the initial set of clinical observations revealed that individuals with aphasia, experiencing damage, for instance, in the Broca's area, displayed impairments localized to this specific brain region. These impairments predominantly affected linguistic functions, sparing other motor or cognitive areas and remaining unaffected by surrounding brain regions. This suggests a modular organization of the mind, where distinct and encapsulated modules operate independently, as Fodor proposed [2].

Additional evidence supports this hypothesis when applying the double dissociation method in developmental disorders. For example, Specific Language Impairment (SLI) is a condition where individuals struggle with language despite having normal hearing and intelligence. They face vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension challenges while other cognitive functions remain intact. Similarly, individuals with Williams Syndrome (WS) may demonstrate deficits in visuospatial tasks while maintaining intact language abilities [3].

This approach is grounded in the classical genetic perspective, suggesting that knowledge, intelligence, and mental disorders are deeply rooted in subtle genetic determinants. According to this view, the environment acts as a trigger, activating pre-existing genetic programs. Additionally, cognitive systems undergo significant reconfiguration at an early age, often before three years old, during a critical development period. During this time, the brain undergoes major transformations that shape long-term cognitive development. It is widely accepted that if this reconfiguration does not occur correctly during this critical phase, it becomes extremely difficult, if not impossible, to recover lost cognitive abilities at a later age. Thus, the early years of life are paramount in establishing the foundations of cognitive development, underscoring the crucial significance of early interventions in addressing developmental disorders.

The neuroconstructivist perspective, however, has raised doubts about the findings of the double dissociation method. By subjecting individuals with Williams syndrome and SLI to meticulous cognitive tasks, deficits have been identified in areas previously considered unaffected in these populations. For instance, it has been revealed that individuals with Williams syndrome may have compromised language abilities, while those with SLI may exhibit deficits in intelligence [4]. This challenges prior assumptions about cognitive modules and maintains that the specificity of cognitive domains and their impairment result from ontogenetic development. It suggests that the notion of intact performance depends on the sensitivity of the measurement scale [5]. Furthermore, domain specificity results from the interactions of various factors, not only genetic but also environmental, the intradynamic nature of the cognitive and emotional systems, and the effects of genetic mutations during embryogenesis and postnatal brain growth. This implies that the specificity of domains and impairments results from cognitive development driven by the complex and dynamic interactions among the abovementioned factors.

Thus, it appears difficult to pinpoint a single domain as impaired; instead, discussing domains that may be affected more subtly than others is more appropriate. Given that the specificity of cognitive domains is a process of constructivist development, termed by Karmiloff-Smith as "modularisation" and by Carey as "specification," this approach calls for a more optimistic outlook. It suggests referring to sensitive periods of development rather than critical periods, as there may be opportunities to recover specific competencies at any age. Instead of discussing the closure and encapsulation of cognitive domains, it emphasizes their rewiring and scaffolding relationships. Furthermore, it advocates substituting a damaged brain area with another within the framework of cerebral plasticity.

In this way, by leveraging cognitive flexibility and cerebral plasticity, constructivist neurology offers new horizons for the effectiveness of cognitive remediation approaches for dysfunctions. These approaches do not solely focus on a specific damaged domain but rather seek to harness the support of another less affected or competent domain. For instance, in neurodegenerative disorders like Parkinson's disease, occupational therapy targets executive functions, motor skills, and emotional states, enabling some patients to regain control over their mental, emotional, and motor states [6].

The same approach also characterizes current psychotherapies, where for most clinical cases such as borderline personality disorder and bipolar disorder, the focus is not solely on addressing dysfunctions in the limbic system and the patient's emotional states, but also on their cognitive performance and executive functions in prefrontal cortex, as well as motor systems in motor areas .

Certainly! If we delve into cognitive development and cerebral functioning, we can discern two overarching dynamics, each comprising a suite of cognitive mechanisms. It's imperative to hone in on these mechanisms for remediation and practical

application, particularly in educational interventions for typical children or in crafting therapeutic protocols for children grappling with neurodevelopmental or dysfunctional disorders.

The first dynamic, the impoverishment dynamic [7], entails understanding that acquiring new knowledge requires a reduction in pre-existing knowledge among children, which may hinder the emergence of fresh insights. Impoverishing specific knowledge facilitates the seamless functioning of working memory and sequential processing, thus safeguarding children from cognitive interference. This process is particularly beneficial for children with dysfunctional disorders, as it enhances their learning abilities.

Among the mechanisms of cognitive functioning that fall within this impoverishment dynamic are inhibition [8], refinement, elimination [9], specification [10], differentiation, modularisation [11], and vicariance of knowledge and skills [12,13]. Their presence or absence plays a pivotal role in the Learning process.

The second dynamic, enrichment, illustrates that our minds operate with specific synergies that connect various cognitive domains. Among the mechanisms belonging to this dynamic, we find fusion, which ensures conceptual change—a crucial process for innovation, especially when well integrated. For instance, Einstein fused physics and mathematics to create theoretical physics [14,15]. Another mechanism is bridging, which facilitates communication and the exchange of information and skills between different cognitive domains without necessarily merging them. Additionally, scaffolding occurs when one competence supports the functioning of another [16]. Lastly, there's the generalization [17,18], where competence is applied across various contexts and domains. All these mechanisms should be considered in therapeutic interventions, especially cognitive remediation and educational actions. Consequently, understanding these dynamics suggests that our intelligence functions not as separate modules but as a network, leading to the concept of network intelligence.

Therefore, the collaboration and networking of various disciplines, such as occupational therapy, psychology, neurology, and psychiatry [19-21], are crucial for addressing the complex challenges posed by cognitive dysfunction. These disciplines can develop cost-effective and efficient therapeutic protocols that leverage cognitive flexibility and cerebral plasticity principles by working together. This interdisciplinary approach enhances our understanding of cognitive processes. It offers new horizons for the effective treatment of cognitive disorders, ultimately improving the quality of life for individuals affected by these conditions.

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